

D1.3 Report on submitted papers

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COVER PAGE

PROJECT	
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Deliverable Author(s):	Elona Pojani (UT), Sasa Petkovic (UBL), Marija Radosavljevic (FEUN), Stojan Debarliev (USK)

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1.0	15/11/2025	First version prepared	Marija Radosavljevic (FEUN)
2.0	30/11/2025	Second version prepared	Sasa Petkovic (UBL)
3.0	10/12/2025	Third version prepared	Stojan Debarliev (USK), Elona Pojani (UT)
4.0	29/12/2025	Quality review	DC and SAB member
Final	30/12/2025	Final version submitted to the EC	Marija Radosavljevic (FEUN)

DISCLAIMER

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ACRONYMS

Acronym	Full name
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FEUN	Faculty of Economics University of Niš
PC	Project Coordinator
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
UBL	University of Banja Luka
USK	St. Cyril & Methodius University in Skopje
UT	University of Tirana
WP	Work Package

INTRODUCTION

This deliverable represents the result of activities carried out within Work Package WP1, which is dedicated to collecting, analyzing, and initiating the dissemination of scientific results generated during the implementation of the project. The deliverable is based on the activities completed in the earlier phases of WP1, including the implementation of secondments, the organization of focus groups, the execution of the Delphi study, as well as a detailed needs analysis conducted among key stakeholder groups. These activities provided the methodological and substantive foundation for preparing the earliest scientific papers within the project.

This report includes papers prepared and submitted by members of the research teams from the partner institutions participating in the USEIPM project. The scientific papers represent a key channel for sharing preliminary research findings, validating the methodological approach, and enhancing the visibility of the project within relevant academic and professional communities. In this way, this deliverable represents an important component of the project's broader dissemination strategy, as it documents progress in publishing results and contributes to increasing the scientific and societal visibility of project activities.

Special attention has been given to ensuring compliance with the policies of the European Commission under the Horizon Europe programme, particularly with regard to Open Access. All partners have ensured open access to publications through submission and publication in open-access journals (Gold Open Access). Authors have also clearly indicated the project's funding in all publications, in accordance with Horizon Europe guidelines. Therefore, this deliverable not only monitors the number and status of submitted papers but also ensures adherence to the rules of transparency, accessibility, and knowledge management established under the Horizon Europe framework.

SUMMARY

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide an overview of the scientific papers submitted by the project's academic partners during the reporting period, documenting the early dissemination of research results generated within the USEIPM project. As part of the broader dissemination and communication strategy, the deliverable serves to track the progress of scientific output and ensure alignment with Horizon Europe requirements regarding visibility, openness, and transparency.

A total of **35 scientific papers** were submitted by all academic partners involved in the project. These submissions reflect the collaborative efforts of the research teams and stem from the findings of previous WP1 activities, including secondments, focus groups, Delphi studies, and the needs analysis. In this way, the planned number of submitted journal papers (22) has been significantly exceeded.

The submitted papers represent significant early result in terms of scientific contribution and project visibility. They demonstrate the relevance of the project's research agenda,

validate the methodological approaches adopted across work packages, and increase the project's presence within relevant academic and professional communities. Moreover, the ensured adherence to Open Access principles enhances the societal impact of the project by making its findings accessible to a broader audience.

DATA COLLECTION METHODOLOGY

The data collection within the USE IPM project was conducted through a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods, designed to cover various aspects of innovation ecosystems, sustainable and responsible innovation, technology transfer, open innovation, and academia-to-business (A2B) collaboration. These methods were specifically adapted to the local contexts of the participating countries, allowing for an in-depth understanding of local needs, barriers, and capacities for research and innovation.

Data were collected through **secondments at non-academic partner organizations**, which provided direct insight into real-world challenges and best practices in business environments. During the secondments, participants engaged in practical activities within companies and innovation centers, documenting and analyzing key success factors and obstacles in innovation processes. Additionally, **focus groups** with experts from different sectors and countries identified key actors in innovation ecosystems, existing challenges in academia-industry collaboration, training and educational needs, and strategies for enhancing sustainable and responsible innovation.

Through **Delphi studies**, project partners gathered expert consensus on innovation processes, A2B collaboration, technology transfer, intellectual property, and sustainable innovation. Experts evaluated key phases of the innovation process, tools and methods used, as well as factors influencing the success of academia-business collaboration, including regulatory, infrastructural, and educational aspects.

Needs analysis was employed to quantitatively assess priorities and challenges in innovation processes and sustainable practices across participating countries. This analysis identified key actors in innovation ecosystems, evaluated the importance of different innovation process phases, assessed the use of innovation management tools, and highlighted obstacles to sustainable and responsible innovation. The results provided a foundation for defining specific areas where targeted training programs and support initiatives were needed.

The integration of these four methods allowed for the collection of a comprehensive dataset that reflects both practical experiences from real business environments and expert opinions, as well as quantified local innovation priorities. This approach ensured a reliable and valid basis for developing training programs, improving technology transfer, fostering sustainable innovations, and enhancing academia-business collaboration in the Western Balkans.

Instruments and Tools Used

- **Secondments:** Provided real-world examples and identified key challenges in business environments, enabling the collection of practical insights.
- **Focus Groups:** Offered expert and practitioner perspectives, identifying critical actors in innovation ecosystems, challenges, and training needs.
- **Delphi Studies:** Enabled expert consensus on innovation processes, open innovation, A2B collaboration, technology transfer, and sustainable innovation.
- **Needs Analysis:** Quantified and statistically evaluated priorities, challenges, and key success factors within each project area.

This integrated methodology generated a reliable and comprehensive dataset, reflecting the activities and knowledge gained across all four thematic areas of the project (1.8 – development of soft skills; 2.8 – sustainability and reporting; 3.8 – technology transfer and open innovation; 4.8 – sustainable and responsible innovation through academia-business collaboration). It provides a solid foundation for designing training programs, enhancing A2B collaboration, and disseminating USE IPM project results.

Data Analysis and Statistical Tools

Collected data were analysed using a combination of descriptive and inferential statistical methods to identify patterns, trends, and correlations relevant to innovation processes, sustainable and responsible practices, and A2B collaboration. Commonly used statistical tools in business management were applied, including:

- **Descriptive statistics:** Means, medians, standard deviations, and frequency distributions to summarize survey and needs analysis results.
- **Cross-tabulations and contingency tables:** To examine relationships between different types of actors, innovation phases, and challenges.
- **Correlation analysis (Pearson and Spearman):** To assess the strength and direction of relationships between variables such as innovation tools usage, team dynamics, and organizational outcomes.
- **Regression analysis (linear and logistic):** To explore factors influencing the success of sustainable innovations and effective academia-business collaboration.
- **ANOVA (Analysis of Variance):** To compare group differences across countries, sectors, or organizational types regarding innovation priorities and obstacles.
- **Cluster analysis:** To segment organizations or regions based on innovation capacity, adoption of responsible practices, or resource availability.
- **Benchmarking and KPI analysis:** Using indicators like number of start-ups, attracted investments, innovations introduced, and market readiness to assess performance and impact.

These statistical analyses provided a robust and objective basis for identifying priorities, challenges, and opportunities in innovation management and for designing targeted interventions and training programs.

THE LIST OF SUBMITTED / PUBLISHED PAPERS

No.	Paper info: Authors, Title, Journal	Submission date	Current status (submitted / under review / accepted / published)	Beneficiary
1.	Đorđević, B., Milanović Zbiljić, S., & Radosavljević, M. (2025). Impact of the Digital Skills on Employability: Cross-Sectional Analysis. <i>Economies</i> , 13(7), 196. https://doi.org/10.3390/economies13070196	03.05.2025	Published	FEUN
2.	Anđelković, A., Radosavljević, M., Milanović Zbiljić, S., Petković, S., Debarliev, S., & Grabova, P. (2025). Assessing the Importance of Soft Skills Development for Shaping Future Entrepreneurs: Insights from a Delphi Study in Western Balkan Countries. <i>Administrative Sciences</i> , 15(12), 457. https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci15120457	24.09.2025	Published	FEUN
3.	Andjelković, A., Janković Milić, V., Radosavljević, M., Petković, S., Kule, D., & Debarliev, S. (2025). Sustainable Entrepreneurship in the Western Balkan Countries: Key Constraints. <i>Sustainability</i> , 17(21), 9406. https://doi.org/10.3390/su17219406	11.09.2025	Published	FEUN
4.	Brajdic, I., Stoilkovic Randjelovic, A., Radosavljevic, M. (2024) Analysis of the Elements of Process Orientation and its Influence on the Profitability of Companies in the Republic of Serbia, <i>Economic Themes</i> (2024) 62(4): 485-502, https://doi.org/10.2478/ethemes-2024-0026	15.09.2024	Published	FEUN
5.	Andjelković, A., Milovanović, G., Milanović, S., Stojanović, D. (2025). Business Ambience for Implementing Just-in-Sequence strategy – The Automotive Industry in Serbia: Case Study. <i>Journal of Business Economics and Management</i> , 26(6), 1243–1263.	05.03.2025	Published	FEUN

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	https://doi.org/10.3846/jbem.2025.25440			
6.	Andjelković, A. Outsourcing in the supply chain as a driver of vulnerability - The case of the Republic of Serbia, <i>South African Journal of Business Management</i>	25.03.2025	Accepted	FEUN
7.	Milanović Zbiljić, S., Đorđević, B., & Radosavljević, M. Predicting Entrepreneurial Intentions Through Entrepreneurship Education: A Theory of Planned Behaviour-Based Analysis, <i>Economic Themes</i>	September 23, 2025	Under review	FEUN
8.	Petrović, J., & Marić, M. (2024). The Importance of Soft Skills for Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises – Evidence from Bosnia and Herzegovina. <i>Journal of Contemporary Economics</i> , 8(1), 90-104. https://doi.org/10.7251/JOCE2408045P90 .	Decembar 20, 2024	Published	UBL
9.	Mičić, L., & Milanović Zbiljić, S. (2025). The Role of Digital Workplace Transformation in Enhancing Organizational Sustainability: A Post-Pandemic Analysis. <i>Journal of Contemporary Economics</i> , 9(1), 17–41. https://doi.org/10.7251/JOCE2509017M .	July 22, 2025	Published	UBL
10.	Petković, S., Debarliev, S., Janeska-Iliev, A., & Kolaković, M. (2025). Innovation Ecosystem Paradox: How Strong External Support Weakens Project Management—Sustainability Innovation Link. <i>Sustainability</i> , 17(22), 9998. https://doi.org/10.3390/su17229998 .	November 8, 2025	Published	UBL
11.	Petković, S., Petrović, J., Bucevska, V., Radosavljević, M, Pojani, E. (2025). What Drives Successful Sustainable Technology Transfer in Emerging Open Innovation Ecosystems: Insights from Southeast Europe. <i>Management: Journal of Contemporary Management Issues</i> .	September 21, 2025	Accepted	UBL
12.	Mičić, Lj. (2025). University as a Digital Workplace: Implications for Teaching, Research, and Skills Development. <i>Marche – Journal of Applied Economics</i> . AS2025 Special Issue: Education, Skills, and Development. New Frontiers in Learning, Innovation, and Inclusion of Economies.	October 18, 2025	Under review	UBL

13.	Milijević, M., & Marić, M. (2025). Cross-Country Analysis of Sustainability Attitudes in the Western Balkans. <i>Marche – Journal of Applied Economics</i> . AS2025 Special Issue: Education, Skills, and Development. New Frontiers in Learning, Innovation, and Inclusion of Economies.	October 15, 2025	Under review	UBL
14.	Marić, M., Mičić, Lj., Milijević, M., & Bogdanović, M. (2025). Bridging the Skills Gap: The Role of Soft Skills in the Digital Economy. <i>Economic Annals</i> .	June 13, 2025	Under review	UBL
15.	Compagnucci, L., Spigarelli, F., Perugini, F., Iacobucci, D., & Cobis, F. (2025). Does the hub and spoke model matter for university-industry engagement in innovation ecosystems?. <i>The Journal of Technology Transfer</i> , 1-32. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-025-10234-6	15.05.2025	Published	UNIVPM
16.	Arena, G., Bregoli, D., Ferreira, R., Liscio, M. C., & Sospiro, P. (2025). Interregional Trade Estimation as a Case for Economic Integration. <i>Regional Science Policy & Practice</i> , 100269. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rsp.2025.100269	10.06.2025	Published	UNIVPM
17.	Kolaković, M., Turuk, M., Horvatinović, T., and Petković, S.: Painting the whole picture: Connecting new business formation, innovative entrepreneurship, and entrepreneurial ecosystems with unemployment. <i>Oeconomia Copernicana</i>	17.06.2025.	Submitted	IIE
18.	Kolaković, M., Hewitt, M. L., and Nikolić, G.: Intellectual Capital in the Digital Era: Exploring Innovation, Value Creation, and Societal Impact. <i>Journal of Business Paradigms</i>	26.11.2025.	Submitted	IIE
19.	Kolaković, M., Horvatinović, T., and Turčić, I.: The impact of emotions on the evaluation of environmentally damaging business opportunities: An experimental study. <i>International Journal of Contemporary Business and Entrepreneurship</i>	26.11.2025.	Submitted	IIE
20.	Skendaj, A. & Bici, A. (2025). Bridging the soft skills gap for a Sustainable Future: A Comparative Study of Student and Employer Perspectives in Albania. <i>ECONOMIA</i>	25.11.2025	Published	

	<p>MARCHE <i>Journal of Applied Economics</i>. Vol. XLIV, No.2, pages 74-101. https://doi.org/10.57638/3034-8234BRISS Bridging the Soft Skills Gap for a Sustainable Future: A Comparative Study of Student and Employer Perspectives in Albania Economia Marche - Journal of Applied Economics</p>			UT
21.	<p>Bici, A., Spahiu, E., Skendaj, A., Jaupi, F., & Radosavljević. M (2026). The Missing Skills Puzzle: How Soft Skills Impact Entrepreneurial and Business Outcomes. <i>Cogent Business and Management</i></p>	08.12.2025	Submitted	UT
22.	<p>Ditjona Kule, Ogerta Elezaj, From Local to Global: Assessing the Internalization Pathways of SMS-s in Albania, <i>Economia Marche – Journal of Applied Economics</i></p>	03.05.2025	Review process	UT
23.	<p>Ditjona Kule, Alba Skendaj, Hafsa Laci, Eda Spahiu, Technology transfer and Sustainable entrepreneurship in Open innovation ecosystem, Albania case – <i>WSEAS Journals</i></p>	11.12.2025	Submitted	UT
24.	<p>Elona Pojani, Fatma Jaupi, Arjan Tushaj, Kristi Dashi, Vesna Bucevska Mapping Sustainable Entrepreneurship in Albania: A CFA–SEM Approach, <i>Administrative sciences</i></p>	14/12/2025	Submitted	UT
25.	<p>Perseta Grabova, Arjan Tushaj, Brikena Leka, Ditjona Kule, Sasa Petkovic: The Missing Link in Albania’s Innovation System: Evidence on Academia–Business Cooperation and Sustainable Innovation, <i>Administrative sciences</i></p>	12/12/2025	Submitted	UT
26.	<p>Elona Pojani, Perseta Grabova, Etleva Bajrami, Mirela Kamberi, Aligning Albania’s Economic Policy with EU Climate and Energy Goals: Evidence from Multi-Stakeholder Roundtables and Documentary Analysis</p>	13/11/2025	Accepted	UT
27.	<p>Gonçalves, A., Martins, A., Santos, D., Serra, M. Economic Nutrition Label: Advancing Sustainable Tourism and Local, Economies through Mediterranean Diet Products, <i>Tourism & Management Studies</i></p>	22.08.2025	Accepted	UAlg

28.	Imaginário, S., Santos, D., Barros, H., Vairinho, S., Rodrigues, J., Martins, A.I. Dinâmicas de Inovação e Empreendedorismo no Algarve: O Papel da UAlg TEC START, Revista Portuguesa de Estudos Regionais	28.11.2025	Submitted	UAlg
29.	Imaginário, S., Santos, D., Vairinho, S., Barros, H., Rodrigues, J., Martins, A.I. Innovation and Entrepreneurship Dynamics in the Algarve: The Role of UAlg TEC START, Tourism & Management Studies	18.12.2025	Submitted	UAlg
30.	Andjelković, A., Stošić Panić, D., Callejón Gil, A.M., Digital Transformation in the Retail Sector: Effects and Business Performance Analysis, Economic Themes	31.10.2025	Under review	UMA
31.	Callejón Gil, A.M., Angel, M., Kocić, J., Radosavljević, M., Frugal Innovations as a Pathway to Inclusive and Resource-Efficient Entrepreneurship, Facta Universitatis	27.12.2025	Submitted	UMA
32.	Naumoski, A., Bucevska, V. Tocev, T., Tonovska, J. Advancing Sustainability Concepts and Sustainability Reporting in the Western Balkans (WB-4): A Delphi Study on Corporate Practices, Journal of East European Management Studies	05.09.2025	Under review	USK
33.	Bucevska, V., Tocev, T., Ristić Cakić, M., Macro drivers of national innovation in Southeast Europe: a cross-country panel, Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship	03.09.2025	In Review	USK
34.	Debarliev, S., Drakulevski, Lj. Bucevska, V., Kitanovikj B., Which sustainability strategies pay? Unbundling the triple bottom line in companies, Cogent Business & Management	01.10.2025	Under review	USK
35.	Stojan Debarliev, Aleksandra Janeska Iliev, Saša Petković, Marija Radosavljević, Ditjona Kule, From Symbiosis to Sustainability: University-Linked Centers as Catalysts in Academy to Business Ecosystems, Int. J. of Entrepreneurship and Small Business	17.12.2025	Under review	USK

SUBMITTED AND PUBLISHED PAPERS' ABSTRACTS INCLUDING LINKS TO THE PUBLISHED PAPERS OR PROOFS OF ACCEPTANCE

1. Đorđević, B., Milanović Zbiljić, S., & Radosavljević, M. (2025). Impact of the Digital Skills on Employability: Cross-Sectional Analysis. *Economies*, 13(7), 196.

Abstract

Digital skills are increasingly vital for enhancing employability, as they equip individuals to meet the evolving demands of the modern workforce. Therefore, this paper examines the impact of digital skills on employability, focusing on the influence of both basic and above-basic levels of information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, problem-solving, digital content creation, and safety skills, considered key components of digital competence. The research employs regression analysis using secondary data extracted from the Eurostat database. Based on data from 32 European countries, the findings indicate that three proxies for digital skills, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, and safety, significantly and positively influence employability. The contribution of this paper to the existing literature on digital skills and employability is twofold. First, by evaluating the influence of five categories of digital skills across different proficiency levels on employment rates, the study sheds light on which specific digital skills have the most substantial impact on employability in today's labor market. Second, the findings provide a foundation for formulating recommendations aimed at enhancing the digital capabilities of the labor force.

Keywords: digital skills; employability; employment rate; European countries

Link: <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7099/13/7/196>

2. Anđelković, A., Radosavljević, M., Milanović Zbiljić, S., Petković, S., Debarliev, S., & Grabova, P. (2025). Assessing the Importance of Soft Skills Development for Shaping Future Entrepreneurs: Insights from a Delphi Study in Western Balkan Countries. *Administrative Sciences*, 15(12), 457.

Abstract

This article explores experts' perspectives on the most important soft skills for entrepreneurial success in the Western Balkans (WB) and identifies effective educational and workplace practices to foster these skills. Using a qualitative Delphi study supported by a literature review, the research gathered and synthesized opinions from 20 experts representing Serbia, Albania, North Macedonia, and Bosnia and Herzegovina. Findings show that communication, adaptability, flexibility, teamwork, and critical thinking are essential for business success, while leadership, emotional intelligence, problem-solving, and teamwork are considered most vital for future entrepreneurs. Experts emphasized that group projects, specialized courses, and blended learning approaches are effective in educational settings, while workplace skill

development benefits from training programs, mentoring, active communication, and openness to feedback. This study provides region-specific insights into skill-building strategies for young entrepreneurs, addressing a key research gap. By integrating expert consensus with evidence-based practices, the article offers a framework for educators, policymakers, institutions, and businesses to strengthen entrepreneurship education and workforce readiness across the WB region.

Keywords: soft skills; Delphi study; entrepreneurship; education; training

Link: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3387/15/12/457>

3. Andjelković, A., Janković Milić, V., Radosavljević, M., Petković, S., Kule, D., & Debarliev, S. (2025). Sustainable Entrepreneurship in the Western Balkan Countries: Key Constraints. *Sustainability*, 17(21), 9406.

Abstract

Public concern about environmental issues has led to growing interest in sustainability across various sectors, including entrepreneurship. However, beyond the concern for environmental protection and the preservation of natural resources for future generations, additional conditions are necessary to foster the development of sustainable entrepreneurship. While developed countries provide examples and evidence of the successful implementation of this concept, its application in developing countries presents challenges due to a range of limiting factors. In addition to essential financial support, the literature often highlights the lack and/or complexity of sustainability reporting, the absence of standards and clearly defined sustainability metrics, insufficient regulation, and the lack of support from higher education institutions as barriers to the transition toward sustainable entrepreneurship. This paper aims to examine the feasibility of applying the concept of sustainable entrepreneurship in Western Balkan countries, taking into account the aforementioned constraints. For the purpose of the empirical research, potential limitations were evaluated by managers and business owners in Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, and Serbia. The results of the study answer the question of whether developing countries have the potential to foster sustainable entrepreneurship, given the analyzed constraints, or whether the implementation of this concept is reserved solely for large enterprises and economically advanced countries.

Keywords: sustainability; sustainable entrepreneurship; development; innovation; Western Balkans

Link: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/17/21/9406>

4. Brajdic, I., Stoiljkovic Randjelovic, A., Radosavljevic, M. (2024) Analysis of the Elements Of

Process Orientation and its Influence on the Profitability of Companies in the Republic of Serbia, *Economic Themes* (2024) 62(4): 485-502

Abstract

The fourth industrial revolution represents a challenge for most companies in terms of creating new business models that will be more flexible, adaptable and dynamic. This is why business process management has become an area of highest priority for most companies in recent years. Business process management can lead to business success by applying process orientation. Thousands of companies have adopted a process meaning. Business process-oriented companies outperform competitors in terms of financial and non-financial performance. Despite the topicality of the issue of process orientation, there is a lack of research on its presence in companies in the Republic of Serbia. The subject of this paper is the research of process orientation through the analysis of the key factors of Business Process Management and their impact on the profitability of the company.

Keywords: Business angels, angel investment, entrepreneurship

Link: <http://xn---itbaba0aapeekb4br.xn--90a3ac/pdf/et20244-4.pdf>

5. Andjelković, A., Milovanović, G., Milanović, S., Stojanović, D. (2025). Business Ambience for Implementing Just-in-Sequence strategy – The Automotive Industry in Serbia: Case Study. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 26(6), 1243–1263.

Abstract

Persistent issues in the automotive industry – such as delivery delays and frequent stock-outs – indicate that the vision of perfectly synchronized flows of raw materials, parts, and components within complex industrial production and logistics systems remains a significant challenge. To mitigate demand variability and uncertainty, companies often maintain high levels of safety stock, which significantly increases costs and erodes competitiveness. At the same time, such supply chains are characterized by limited responsiveness, resulting in unfulfilled targets related to reduced lead times and reliable customer deliveries. As a response, supply chains in the automotive sector are increasingly opting for the implementation of Just-in-Sequence (JIS) strategies to ensure adaptation to diverse product requirements and cost savings, as well as enhance both responsiveness and efficiency. Within this context, the objective of this research is to identify key elements necessary for the successful implementation of the JIS strategy in an automotive company. The research findings reveal notable differences in the perceptions of employees from Production, Logistics, and Sales sectors regarding the importance of the analysed variables and the potential for implementing a JIS strategy.

Keywords: Just-in-sequence, Just-in-time, supply chain, lead time, automotive, variables

Link: <https://doi.org/10.3846/jbem.2025.25440>

6. Andjelković, A. Outsourcing in the supply chain as a driver of vulnerability - The case of the Republic of Serbia, South African Journal of Business Management

Abstract

Purpose: Outsourcing is a widely used supply strategy for activities in which firms lack sufficient or appropriate competencies. While it enhances efficiency, extensive outsourcing may reduce transparency and control, thereby limiting firms' ability to detect disruptions and increasing supply chain vulnerability. This study examines to what extent outsourcing contributes to supply chain vulnerability in the context of the Republic of Serbia.

Design/methodology/approach: An empirical survey was conducted among 52 large enterprises from various sectors in Serbia, all of which were listed among the most successful based on their net profit. Hypotheses were tested using statistical methods, specifically the χ^2 test, cluster analysis, ANOVA and linear regression in SPSS.

Findings/results: The survey results indicate that the proportion of outsourced activities did not significantly affect supply chain vulnerability ($p = 0.695$ and $p = 0.556$), while greater dispersion of outsourced activities ($p = 0.005$ and $p = 0.003$) and higher supply chain complexity ($p = 0.014$ and $p = 0.007$) were statistically significant. These findings suggest that although the share of outsourced activities alone does not increase vulnerability, both dispersion and complexity significantly elevate it.

Practical implications: These findings do not argue against outsourcing but emphasize the importance of enhanced risk management and contingency planning.

Originality/value: This pilot study provides initial empirical evidence on the impact of specific outsourcing activities on supply chain vulnerability. It also lays the foundation for future research, potentially extending to broader studies across the Western Balkans, given the similar business context and interconnections among enterprises in the region.

Keywords: outsourcing, vulnerability, supply chain, risk

[ET] Submission Acknowledgement

September 23, 2025 9:39 PM

From: ekonomske-teme

To: Sandra Milanović Zbiljić

Sandra Milanović Zbiljić:

Thank you for submitting the manuscript, "PREDICTING ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS THROUGH ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION: A THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOUR-BASED ANALYSIS" to [Economic Themes](#). With the online journal management system that we are using, you will be able to track its progress through the editorial process by logging in to the journal web site:

Submission URL: <https://publishing.eknfak.ni.ac.rs/index.php/economic-themes/authorDashboard/submission/55>

Username: mzsandra

If you have any questions, please contact me. Thank you for considering this journal as a venue for your work.

Dragana Radenković Jocić

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8. Petrović, J., & Marić, M. (2024). The Importance of Soft Skills for Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises – Evidence from Bosnia and Herzegovina. *Journal of Contemporary Economics*, 8(1), 90-104. <https://doi.org/10.7251/JOCE2408045P90>.

Abstract

This article investigates the importance of soft skills for starting and successfully running small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH). Using data collected from a survey of 71 upper-level managers from enterprises operating in BiH, complemented by qualitative insights from a focus group on the same subject, the study examines the perception of importance of the skills such as leadership, communication, emotional intelligence, problem-solving, and teamwork. Statistical analyses, including descriptive analysis, Spearman correlation coefficients, Chi-square tests, and Fisher's Exact tests, reveal that most soft skills are highly valued by SMEs, with slight differences in perceived importance. Communication skills emerged as the most important, reflecting their central role in fostering productive business interactions. The conducted analyses also indicate that the desirable set of soft skills does not change with the company size, except for the leadership skill. Leadership shows a moderate positive correlation with company size, indicating its increasing importance in larger organizations. Qualitative findings confirm the importance of soft skills for starting and managing businesses, with emphasis on communication and problem-solving skills.

Keywords: soft skills, small and medium sized enterprises, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Link: <https://www.swotjournal.com/index.php/casopis/article/view/16>

9. Mičić, L., & Milanović Zbiljić, S. (2025). The Role of Digital Workplace Transformation in Enhancing Organizational Sustainability: A Post-Pandemic Analysis. *Journal of Contemporary Economics*, 9(1), 17–41. <https://doi.org/10.7251/JOCE2509017M>.

Abstract

The increasing adoption of digital workplace technologies has significantly reshaped organizational operations, particularly in the post-pandemic era. Digital transformation has become a key enabler of business sustainability by improving efficiency, reducing operational costs, and fostering remote and hybrid work models. However, the relationship between digital workplace strategies and organizational sustainability remains underexplored, particularly in the context of long-term adaptation and resilience. This study examines how digital workplace transformation contributes to sustainability by analyzing its impact on employee productivity, collaboration, and environmental resource optimization. The research employs a mixed-method approach, combining a systematic literature review with case studies of organizations that have successfully implemented digital workplace strategies. Secondary data from industry reports, academic publications, and surveys provide insights into the benefits and challenges associated with digital workplace adoption. The findings reveal that digital workplace tools enhance employee engagement and productivity while also contributing to environmental sustainability by reducing office-related energy consumption and commuting emissions. The study underscores the need for organizations to integrate digital workplace transformation into their long-term sustainability strategies. It highlights the role of artificial intelligence, cloud computing, and knowledge management systems in enhancing digital collaboration and innovation. The results offer practical implications for business leaders and policymakers aiming to develop resilient and sustainable organizations in the digital era.

Keywords: digital workplace, sustainability, digital transformation, post-pandemic

Link: <https://www.swotjournal.com/index.php/casopis/article/view/27>

10. Petković, S., Petrović, J., Bucevska, V., Radosavljević, M, Pojani, E. (2025). What Drives Successful Sustainable Technology Transfer in Emerging Open Innovation Ecosystems: Insights from Southeast Europe. *Management: Journal of Contemporary Management Issues*.

Abstract

Limited resources on the planet and the increasing demand for promoting sustainable development at a global level have compelled businesses of all sizes, particularly micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), to implement sustainable innovations and transition from a linear to a circular economy. Given the limited resources in start-ups and SMEs (such as Research and Development (R&D), financial, and human resources), they are increasingly forced to collaborate with various stakeholders, including universities, governmental and non-governmental institutions and organizations, institutions of the entrepreneurial infrastructure, and other actors in open innovation ecosystems (OIE). This research aims to gain deeper insights into the challenges and opportunities of sustainable technology transfer and sustainable entrepreneurship in emerging open innovation ecosystems within developing transitional economies in the Southeast Europe, and to propose sustainable cooperation models within OIEs in transitional economies. A comprehensive mixed-research methodology was applied, including a needs analysis, focus group research, a Delphi study, as well as quantitative research on a sample of 100 companies from four Southeast European countries. These were analysed and the research hypotheses were tested using the PLS-SEM-NCA method. The implications of our research are threefold. From a theoretical perspective, the complex and comprehensive methodological approach, which investigates the needs of the real sector and the academic community for closer academia-to-business (A2B) collaboration within emerging open innovation ecosystems, as well as peer-to-peer collaboration among companies, offers a concrete contribution to the theory of open innovation. Additionally, political implications and recommendations for managers are proposed.

Keywords: Sustainable entrepreneurship, technology transfer, R&D and IPP, transitional economies, commercialization of innovation

Editor Decision Спољни Примљено x

Nikša Alfrević via HRČAK OJS : Open access journals system hrcak@srce.hr 21. 9. 2025. 09:06 ☆ ↶ ⋮
коме ја ▾

Изгледа да је ова порука на језику: енглески ×
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Saša Petković, Jadranka Petrović, Vesna Bucevska, Marija Radosavljević, Elona Pojani:

We have reached a decision regarding your submission to Management : Journal of Contemporary Management Issues, "What Drives Successful Sustainable Technology Transfer in Emerging Open Innovation Ecosystems : Insights from Southeast Europe".

Our decision is to: Accept Submission

↶ Одговори ➔ Проледи

11. Petković, S., Debarliev, S., Janeska-Iliev, A., & Kolaković, M. (2025). Innovation Ecosystem Paradox: How Strong External Support Weakens Project Management—Sustainability

Innovation Link. *Sustainability*, 17(22), 9998. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17229998>.

Abstract

This study examines the impact of structured internal innovation project management (IPM) practices and external innovation ecosystem (IE) characteristics on sustainable and responsible innovation (SRI) in EU widening countries. Using a two-stage Delphi-informed survey of 100 firms across Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Albania, and Serbia, the research applies moderated multiple regression analysis to examine the interplay between internal processes and external ecosystem maturity. Results show that both structured innovation phases and tools have a positive impact on SRI. However, while innovation phases consistently enhance SRI regardless of ecosystem conditions, the effect of innovation tools weakens in stronger ecosystems, suggesting a resource substitution dynamic. These findings challenge the assumption that greater ecosystem support uniformly improves innovation outcomes. The study contributes to the theoretical integration of the Resource-Based View and Innovation Ecosystem Theory, highlighting context-specific conditions in transitional economies. Practical implications are offered for managers and policymakers; firms in weaker ecosystems should prioritize building internal innovation capabilities, while those in mature ecosystems may gain more from leveraging external collaborations. The research advances debates on sustainable innovation strategies by showing how the effectiveness of internal management practices depends on ecosystem maturity, offering insights for both policy interventions and strategic innovation management in developing economies.

Keywords: sustainable innovation; responsible innovation; innovation tools; ecosystem moderation; EU widening countries

Link: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/17/22/9998>

12. Mičić, Lj. (2025). University as a Digital Workplace: Implications for Teaching, Research, and Skills Development. *Marche – Journal of Applied Economics*. AS2025 Special Issue: Education, Skills, and Development. *New Frontiers in Learning, Innovation, and Inclusion of Economia*.

Abstract

The rapid digital transformation of higher education has redefined the university as a digital workplace, reshaping its core missions of teaching, research, and skills development. This paper provides a literature-based analysis of how universities integrate digital tools, platforms, and processes into academic work, with a particular focus on their impact on pedagogical practices, research collaboration, and the cultivation of students' transversal competencies. Building on recent studies and international policy reports, the paper examines the interplay between digital infrastructures (e.g., learning management systems, collaborative research platforms, and knowledge management tools) and the organizational culture of universities. The findings suggest that digitalization not only enhances flexibility and efficiency in academic work but also poses challenges related to faculty readiness, digital skills gaps, and the risk of work intensification. By framing the university as a digital workplace, the paper highlights both

opportunities and tensions that emerge from the integration of artificial intelligence, online collaboration, and hybrid teaching models. The analysis contributes to the ongoing debate on how higher education institutions can strategically navigate digital transformation to foster inclusive, adaptive, and skill-oriented learning environments.

Keywords: Digital transformation; University workplace; Higher education; Teaching and research; Skills development

EMJ Editor Decision

1 message

Noemi Giampaoli <n.giampaoli@univpm.it> Sat, Oct 18, 2025 at 10:36 AM

To: Ljubisa Micic <ljubisa.micic@ef.unibl.org>

Ljubisa Micic:

We have reached a decision regarding your submission to *Economia Marche - Journal of Applied Economics*, "Title: University as a Digital Workplace: Implications for Teaching, Research, and Skills Development".

Our decision is: Conditional Acceptance – Minor Revisions Required.

Please note that the requested revisions are minor and do not require substantial changes to the structure or content of your paper. The current version is already strong and well-written — the suggested points are meant only to refine and strengthen specific aspects of the manuscript.

We would also like to remind you that your paper is classified as a short paper. Points aim to provide some suggestions for improving the work before submission but, please, respect the length of the manuscript.

We kindly ask you to submit the revised version by the end of the month, so that, once completed, your contribution can be included in the special issue.

Thank you once again for your excellent work and cooperation.

EconomiaMarche - *Economia Marche Journal of Applied Economic*

13. Miljević, M., & Marić, M. (2025). Cross-Country Analysis of Sustainability Attitudes in the Western Balkans. *Marche – Journal of Applied Economics*. AS2025 Special Issue: Education, Skills, and Development. *New Frontiers in Learning, Innovation, and Inclusion of Economies*.

Abstract

This study examines cross-country differences in sustainability attitudes within the Western Balkans, focusing on Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, and Serbia. Using survey data from 100 respondents (25 per country), we assessed perceptions of environmental, economic, and social aspects of sustainability, as well as perceived challenges, benefits, and practical implementation. The analysis employed the Kruskal–Wallis H test and Dunn’s post-hoc comparisons to identify statistically significant differences and estimate effect sizes. The findings are complemented using the results of the Chi-square test. Results indicate that while sustainability is highly valued in all four countries, notable variations emerge in

environmental priorities, with North Macedonia and Bosnia and Herzegovina reporting the highest ecological awareness, Serbia showing balanced attention across all dimensions, and Albania demonstrating positive attitudes, but lower levels of practical implementation. Differences in economic and social aspects were not statistically significant, suggesting shared regional priorities in these domains. These findings provide a statistical basis for tailoring education and skills policies to support sustainable growth, strengthen social cohesion, and enhance regional cooperation in line with the goals of a just transition and the sustainable, digital transformation of the region.

Keywords: sustainability attitudes; environmental awareness; quantitative analysis; statistical comparison

From: RENGHINI MATTEO <m.renghini@pm.univpm.it>

Date: Wed, Oct 15, 2025 at 14:46 Subject: Revision of manuscript if *Economia Marche*

To: Milica Marić <milica.maric@ef.unibl.org>

Dear Milica Maric'

We have received the referee's report. The referee appreciated your work.

The final decision is *conditionally accepted*, subject to some very minor revisions.

Given the extremely marginal nature of the required changes, we expect to receive your revised manuscript soon, ideally by **October 24**.

The referee's report is attached.

Once you have completed the revision, please upload your manuscript again as you did previously.

Looking forward to hearing from you soon.

Matteo Renghini, Ph.D.

Editorial Board of *Economia Marche* - Journal of Applied Economics

14. Marić, M., Mičić, Lj., Milijević, M., & Bogdanović, M. (2025). Bridging the Skills Gap: The Role of Soft Skills in the Digital Economy. *Economic Annals*.

Abstract

As the digital economy continues to evolve, the demand for human-centric competencies is becoming increasingly critical. This study examines the role of soft skills in bridging the skills gap in modern business environments, with a focus on communication, teamwork, adaptability, and emotional intelligence. Based on a survey of 71 senior managers and executives from diverse business sectors in Bosnia and Herzegovina, the findings indicate that communication skills are the most highly valued, followed closely by teamwork and adaptability. At the same time, emotional intelligence, though important, ranks comparatively lower. To contextualise these insights, the research incorporates ICT adoption data from the Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina (BHAS), exploring how digitalisation is reshaping workforce demands. The observed trends suggest that the need for problem-solving, adaptability, and interpersonal competencies could intensify as automation and digital tools become more integrated into business operations. The study highlights the growing

necessity of interactive, feedback-driven training methods over traditional instructional approaches to develop these skills effectively. Findings provide strategic recommendations for human resource development, educational curricula, and organisational policies to ensure that businesses can cultivate a workforce capable of navigating the challenges of an increasingly digitalised economy.

Keywords: soft skills, digitalisation, workforce demand

----- Forwarded message -----

From: **Nikola Njegovan** <onbehalf@manuscriptcentral.com>

Date: Fri, Jun 13, 2025 at 11:07

Subject: Economic Annals - Manuscript ID EA-2025-0047

To: <milica.maric@ef.unibl.org>

13-Jun-2025

Dear Ms. Maric:

Your manuscript entitled "Bridging the Skills Gap: The Role of Soft Skills in the Digital Economy" has been successfully submitted online and is presently being given full consideration for publication in Economic Annals.

Your manuscript ID is EA-2025-0047.

Please mention the above manuscript ID in all future correspondence or when calling the office for questions. If there are any changes in your street address or e-mail address, please log in to ScholarOne Manuscripts at <https://mc04.manuscriptcentral.com/economicannals> and edit your user information as appropriate.

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15. Compagnucci, L., Spigarelli, F., Perugini, F., Iacobucci, D., & Cobis, F. (2025). Does the hub and spoke model matter for university-industry engagement in innovation ecosystems?. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 1-32.

Abstract

While the literature has extensively investigated applications of the hub-and-spoke (H&S) model, its characteristics, dynamics, effectiveness, and costs remain underexplored in the field of university–industry partnerships for knowledge transfer in innovation ecosystems (IEs). This study contributes to the literature on the organisation of relationships in innovation ecosystems by investigating whether, and in what ways, the H&S model matters in governing partnerships for knowledge transfer.

To achieve this aim, a multiple case study was conducted on 11 national IEs funded by the Italian government under the framework of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan during the period 2022–2026. These ecosystems operate across 20 regions, comprising 11 hubs and 84 spokes, and involving more than 40 universities and over 200 research organisations and firms.

The findings, based on secondary data, two questionnaires, and in-depth interviews with individuals involved in H&S governance, reveal that a top-down approach was adopted since, for the first time, the government mandated the creation of ecosystems structured through the H&S model. The analysed IEs have enhanced collaboration between universities and firms, and related challenges and good practices are discussed.

The article identifies three forms of application of the H&S model, depending on the geographical span of relations between actors: urban, regional, and cross-regional ecosystems. Based on the level of coordination among ecosystem actors, three types of knowledge-transfer governance solutions are conceptualised: centralised, decentralised, and hybrid models.

Finally, implications are offered to improve university governance and inform the design of policies supporting university–industry engagement.

Keywords: Ecosystems of innovation, Hub and spoke, Industrial policy, Knowledge transfer, Next generation EU plan, University–industry cooperation.

Link: <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007/s10961-025-10234-6.pdf>

16. Arena, G., Bregoli, D., Ferreira, R., Liscio, M. C., & Sospiro, P. (2025). Interregional Trade Estimation as a Case for Economic Integration. *Regional Science Policy & Practice*, 100269.

Abstract

This paper examines the estimation of interregional trade as a lens for understanding the broader dynamics of economic integration, with particular emphasis on the persistent “border effect” in the European Union (EU). Although regional integration aims to facilitate seamless economic flows through policy convergence and infrastructural alignment, empirical evidence continues to reveal significant barriers to cross-border trade. These frictions—both tangible and intangible—challenge the assumption of a borderless economy within integrated regions. Through a systematic literature review guided by the PRISMA methodology, the study traces the evolution of trade estimation techniques, focusing on the gravity model as the dominant

analytical framework. The review highlights key methodological innovations, including hybrid gravity–input–output models, RAS calibration, and spatial econometrics, as well as sectoral and regional applications that reveal asymmetries in trade flows. By synthesizing findings from peer-reviewed studies and academic research, the paper underscores the multidimensional nature of border effects and the uneven outcomes of integration policies.

The analysis is complemented by references to grey literature—primarily policy documents—which help situate the societal relevance of the research. The paper concludes that while gravity models remain central to trade analysis, their future relevance depends on incorporating behavioural, infrastructural, governance, and political dimensions. Overall, this work contributes to ongoing academic and policy debates by advocating for a more nuanced, interdisciplinary approach to understanding economic integration in an increasingly fragmented yet interconnected world.

Keywords: Economic Integration, Interregional Trade, Gravity Model, Review

Link: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S175778022500099X>

17. Kolaković, M., Turuk, M., Horvatinović, T., and Petković, S.: Painting the whole picture: Connecting new business formation, innovative entrepreneurship, and entrepreneurial ecosystems with unemployment. *Oeconomia Copernicana*

Abstract

Research background: The relationship between business formation and unemployment has been a topic of scientific discourse for decades. As time progressed, new insights emerged from the increased utilized methodological complexities. Nonetheless, a gap remains in how innovative entrepreneurs respond to changes in unemployment and vice versa. Similarly, there is scarce evidence of the relationship between entrepreneurial ecosystems and unemployment.

Purpose of the article: The purpose of this study is to examine how different measures of regional entrepreneurship impact and are impacted by regional labor market changes.

Methods: Three distinct panel vector autoregression models are carried out on a county-level dataset, with the inclusion of Granger causality tests, orthogonal impulse response functions, and forecast error variance decompositions.

Findings & value added: The results reveal no reverse causality between new business formation, innovative entrepreneurship, and entrepreneurial ecosystems on the one hand and unemployment on the other. They do, however, support two direct relations. One, the formation of new businesses negatively impacts unemployment. Second, unemployment is a negative antecedent of innovative entrepreneurship. Unexpectedly, the entrepreneurial ecosystem autoregressive coefficient is negative. These findings are positioned according to robust explanatory frameworks. Accordingly, the outcomes of this study can be utilized by a broad and diverse set of regional policymakers in devising their strategies to achieve regional

development. One of the key messages is to focus on the long-term and innovative aspects of entrepreneurship, as such policies should lead to lasting and sustainable regional competitiveness. From the entrepreneurs' point of view, the entrepreneurial ecosystem's resilience to external shocks would have provided assurance for a stable regional environment were it not for the persistence of innovative competition and the inability of entrepreneurial ecosystems to operate at a productive level for multiple periods.

Keywords: New business formation; Innovative entrepreneurship; Entrepreneurial ecosystems; Regional entrepreneurship; Unemployment rate

Submission Acknowledgement External Priştigla pošta x

Oeconomia Copernicana via Economic Publishing Platform info@journals.economic-research.pl uto, 17. lip 14:33 ☆ ← ⋮

Tin Horvatinić

Thank you for submitting the manuscript, "Painting the whole picture: Connecting new business formation, innovative entrepreneurship, and entrepreneurial ecosystems with unemployment" to Oeconomia Copernicana. With the online journal management system that we are using, you will be able to track its progress through the editorial process by logging in to the journal web site:

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SNIP 2022: 1.545

SJR 2023: 0.99

Economics, Econometrics and Finance (miscellaneous) / Development: Q1

18. Kolaković, M., Hewitt, M. L., and Nikolić, G.: Intellectual Capital in the Digital Era: Exploring Innovation, Value Creation, and Societal Impact. *Journal of Business Paradigms*

Abstract

This study explores intellectual capital (IC) as a multifaceted, dynamic set of intangible resources integral to organizations: comprising human, structural, relational, and, increasingly, informational capital. In the age of digital transformation and rapid technological innovation, these resources do not remain static; their boundaries continuously shift, informed by emergent technologies, sustainability demands, and evolving connections between organizational competencies. This paper examines how human knowledge, organizational routines, and networks of trust operate together to spark creativity, enable innovation, and foster resilience, and it accounts for the new challenges posed by AI and automation.

Keywords: Intellectual Capital, Digital Transformation, Innovation, Value Creation, Human and Structural Resources

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Journal of Business Paradigms | 2025 | Vol 8.

**PAR University of Applied Sciences
Rijeka, Croatia**

SUBMISSION CONFIRMATION

Paper Title: Intellectual Capital in the Digital Era: Exploring Innovation, Value Creation, and Societal Impact

Authors: Marko Kolakovic, PhD, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Magda Lia Hewitt, PhD, University of Johannesburg, South Africa
Gordana Nikolic, PhD, PAR University Rijeka, Croatia

Date of Submission: November 26, 2025

Status: In Review

This is the confirmation of the receipt of the aforementioned manuscript, submitted for the Journal of Business Paradigms published by the PAR University of Applied Sciences.

19. Kolaković, M., Horvatinović, T., and Turčić, I.: The impact of emotions on the evaluation of environmentally damaging business opportunities: An experimental study. International Journal of Contemporary Business and Entrepreneurship

Abstract

While the literature on affect in entrepreneurship is gaining prominence, the question of how emotions are connected with environmental business opportunity evaluations remains

unanswered. To address such a question, this study utilised an experimental design to test the impact of three discrete emotions (hope, compassion, and anger) on the evaluation of environmentally harmful business opportunities, using a sample of 304 undergraduate students. When the results of the linear mixed model regression and estimated marginal means contrasts are jointly interpreted, anger emerged as the only robust emotional predictor. The effect of hope depends on the type of business opportunity, whereas compassion remains non-significant across all model specifications. These findings underscore the importance of negative emotions, specifically anger, in suppressing the evaluations of harmful entrepreneurial opportunities.

Keywords: Emotions, Environmental Business Opportunities, Entrepreneurship, Experimental Study, Anger

Application for IJCBE Journal

editor@ijcbeonline.com <editor@ijcbeonline.com>
Prima: Ivan Turčić <iturcic@efzg.hr>

26. studenoga 2025. u 22:30

Dear Authors,

Thank you very much for your submission to the International Journal of Contemporary Business and Entrepreneurship (IJCBE).

We hereby confirm receipt of your manuscript entitled "The impact of emotions on the evaluation of environmentally damaging business opportunities: An experimental study." The paper has been successfully registered in our editorial system and will now be assigned to reviewers.

We appreciate your interest in publishing with IJCBE and will keep you informed about the progress of the review process.

Should you need any additional information in the meantime, please feel free to contact us.

Kind regards,

Mladen Turuk, PhD
Editor-in-Chief
International Journal of Contemporary Business and Entrepreneurship (IJCBE)

20. Skendaj, A. & Bici, A. (2025). Bridging the soft skills gap for a Sustainable Future: A Comparative Study of Student and Employer Perspectives in Albania. *ECONOMIA MARCHE Journal of Applied Economics*. Vol. XLIV, No.2, pages 74-101. <https://doi.org/10.57638/3034-8234BRISS>

Abstract

This study investigates the persistent gap between soft skills taught in higher education and those demanded by employers in Albania's evolving innovation and sustainability-oriented economy. Using a mixed-methods approach, the research draws on survey data from 51 university students and 67 company representatives, complemented by a focus group with HR managers across key sectors. Results reveal a strong consensus on the importance of

communication and teamwork, ranked essential by nearly 80% of businesses and over 70% of students, while significant deficits persist in problem solving, self-management, and critical thinking. Only 38.8% of companies provide structured soft skills training, and 53.7% rate new graduates' competencies as only partially sufficient. Students identify group projects as their main source of soft skill development, with limited internship opportunities (17.6%) restricting experiential learning. Focus group insights reinforce that communication, adaptability, and ethical awareness are increasingly decisive for employability and entrepreneurship, yet underdeveloped in formal education. The study contributes new empirical evidence from a transition economy, demonstrating the need for co-designed curricula, systematic soft skill assessment, and sustainability-linked training programs to better align university outcomes with labor market expectations.

Keywords: Soft Skills Gap, Challenges, Sustainability, Teamwork, Problem-solving, Communication

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ECONOMIA MARCHE

VOL. 44 NO. 2 (2025), ARTICLES
Published 2025-11-25

Bridging the Soft Skills Gap for a Sustainable Future: A Comparative Study of Student and Employer Perspectives in Albania

Alba Skendaj
University of Tirana, Faculty of Economy

[EM] Editor Decision

NOEMI GIAMPAOLI

To: alba.skendaj; Noemi Giampaoli + 1

Thu 10/30/2025 10:37 PM [View more](#)

Dear Alba,

Thank you for your message and for sharing the revised version of the paper. I have reviewed the document, and everything appears to be in perfect order. The paper has been accepted - congratulations to you and Ada for your excellent work.

We look forward to receiving further contributions from you in the future.

Kind regards,

Noemi Giampaoli
Economia Marche - Journal of Applied Economics

21. Bici, A., Spahiu, E., Skendaj, A., Jaupi, F., & Radosavljević. M., The Missing Skills Puzzle: How Soft Skills Impact Entrepreneurial and Business Outcomes. *Administrative Sciences, MDPI.*

Abstract

Being competitive and adapting to market changes are pressing issues for today's businesses. Soft skills, also called "noncognitive skills," are important drivers of sustainable business success. This study investigates whether soft skills development is associated with superior entrepreneurial and business performance among companies operating in Albania. Data were collected through a structured survey from managers and decision-makers of 170 firms operating across diverse sectors. The questionnaire was developed through a Delphi study and focus group with experts, as well as reference literature regarding soft skills. Its reliability and validity were confirmed through a pilot test and Cronbach's alpha analysis. Correlation analysis was used to examine the relationships between the variables. The results show that the perceived importance of soft skills, particularly leadership, emotional intelligence, and problem-solving, is positively and significantly associated with non-financial performance indicators such as employee growth, new product development, increased turnover, market share, and overall performance. While leadership and problem-solving are developed in line with their perceived importance from the participants of the study, communication and emotional intelligence reveal a clear perception–practice gap, resulting in underdeveloped competencies in practice. Moderation analyses indicate that company size and industry sector strengthen the relationships between soft skills and business performance, with stronger effects observed in larger and service-oriented firms. The findings provide region-specific insights that confirm the high impact of soft skills on entrepreneurial and business performance and suggest focusing on communication and emotional intelligence skills within both education and organizational training systems. Policymakers should promote skills development through national upskilling programs, projects, and investments in national skill programs.

Keywords: soft skills, entrepreneurial performance, skills development, business outcomes, skills gap, Albania

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08 December 2025	Submission Created
08 December 2025	Submission Incomplete
08 December 2025	Manuscript Submitted
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Thank you for your submission.

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Journal	Cogent Business & Management
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22. Ditjona Kule, Ogerta Elezaj, From Local to Global: Assessing the Internalization Pathways of SMS-s in Albania, *Economia Marche – Journal of Applied Economics*

Abstract

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) constitute an essential part of the global economy and play a significant role in the economic development of countries by creating jobs and fostering innovation. In the era of globalization, internationalization has become a key strategy for the growth and survival of SMEs, especially in rapidly changing markets. Through internationalization, SMEs could expand beyond their local borders, enter new markets, and benefit from the growing number of international consumers.

This study aims to examine the internationalization process of SMEs, with a particular focus on Albanian enterprises and the challenges they face in global markets. It will analyze the main strategies SMEs use to enter international markets, the factors influencing their success or failure, as well as the role of entrepreneurs and government policies in promoting this process. In addition, concrete cases of Albanian SMEs that have successfully internationalized will be presented, highlighting best practices that other enterprises can follow. Through this analysis,

the paper provides recommendations for entrepreneurs and Albanian institutions to improve their policies and strategies in support of SMEs aiming to internationalize.

Keywords: Small and Medium Enterprises, Global Markets, Albanian Enterprises, SME Growth

Proof of Acceptance:

Martina Orci <m.orci@pm.univpm.it>

To: © Ditjona Kule

Wed 9/3/2025 4:53 PM

Ditjona Kule:

We have reached a decision regarding your submission to **Economia Marche** - Journal of Applied Economics, "From From Local to Global: Assessing the Internationalization Pathways of SMEs in Albania".

Our decision is to: Resubmit for Review

Your abstract has been accepted for the Special Issue.

Please submit your short paper for review by 10 October. The short paper must be prepared in an anonymous format. You may upload a separate file with the authors' names.

Kindly note that you should upload the files within the same submission procedure, without opening a new submission.

We look forward to receiving your contribution.

Best regards

23. Ditjona Kule, Alba Skendaj, Hafsa Laci, Eda Spahiu, Technology transfer and Sustainable entrepreneurship in Open innovation ecosystem, Albania case – WSEAS Journals

Abstract

This paper examines the interactions among technology transfer, sustainable entrepreneurship, and open innovation within transitional economies, with a particular focus on Albania. Employing a mixed-methods design, the study integrates quantitative evidence from a structured survey of 204 senior representatives of companies and start-ups with complementary insights from a student–academic survey capturing 30 perceptions from future entrepreneurs and researchers, as well as a focus group with HR managers and entrepreneurs. The findings highlight the pivotal role of universities and research institutions as anchors of the innovation ecosystem, serving not only as generators of knowledge but also as intermediaries that facilitate collaboration and commercialization. Organizational enablers, particularly leadership commitment, innovation culture, and strategic partnerships, emerge as critical drivers of open innovation, while persistent barriers include insufficient financial resources, weak industry–academia collaboration, limited commercialization channels, and deficiencies in intellectual property protection. In parallel, soft skills such as communication, adaptability,

resilience, and critical thinking are identified as essential for building entrepreneurial capacity and sustaining innovation in uncertain environments. The analysis underscores the necessity of targeted financial mechanisms, robust policy frameworks, and digital transformation tools to overcome systemic constraints. By triangulating perspectives across businesses, academia, and human resource experts, the study provides a holistic account of both challenges and opportunities, offering actionable recommendations for policymakers, universities, and entrepreneurs seeking to strengthen resilient and sustainable innovation ecosystems in transitional contexts.

Keywords: Technology transfer, Sustainable entrepreneurship, Open innovation, Transitional economies, Universities and research institutions, Organizational enablers, Entrepreneurial skills.

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24. Elona Pojani, Fatma Jaupi, Arjan Tushaj, Kristi Dashi, Vesna Bucevska, Mapping Sustainable Entrepreneurship in Albania: A CFA–SEM Approach, Administrative sciences

Abstract

This study investigates how sustainable and responsible entrepreneurship is understood, implemented, and potentially expanded within the Albanian business landscape. Empirical data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to sample of 200 Albanian companies. The questionnaire captures multiple dimensions of sustainable entrepreneurship, including environmental practices such as waste and water management, economic aspects such as responsible growth and stakeholder collaboration, and social responsibility initiatives related to employee development, inclusion, and community engagement. To validate the underlying structure of these dimensions, a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), followed by Structural Equations Modelling was conducted, providing statistical support for the key constructs that shape sustainable entrepreneurship in the Albanian context. Overall, the findings suggest that Albanian businesses are increasingly aware of the importance of sustainable entrepreneurship and recognize the potential of circular economy and sustainability reporting. However, the realization of this potential, hinges on enhancing internal capabilities, particularly IT support and strategic orientation, while simultaneously improving the institutional environment, especially for smaller firms, so that sustainability can become a mainstream driver of inclusive and resilient development.

Keywords: Sustainable entrepreneurship, Albania, Structural Equation Modelling, drivers, barriers

Manuscript ID	Journal	Section / Special Issue	Title	Status	Submission Date
admsci-4071978 B	Administrative Sciences		Mapping Sustainable Entrepreneurship in Albania: A CFA–SEM Approach	Pending review	2025-12-14 14:10:45

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Received: 14 Dec 2025
E-mails: elona.pojani@unitir.edu.al, fatma.jaupi@unitir.edu.al, arjan.tushaj@unitir.edu.al, kristi.dashi@unitir.edu.al, vesna@eccf.ukim.edu.mk

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25. Perseta Grabova, Arjan Tushaj, Ditjona Kule, Brikena Leka, Saša Petković, The Missing Link in Albania's Innovation System: Evidence on Academia–Business Cooperation and Sustainable Innovation, Administrative sciences

Abstract

This article investigates how collaboration between academia and business (A2B) contributes to sustainable innovation in Albania, a small transition economy with an immature innovation system but growing digital and green ambitions. Drawing on innovation systems and resource-based perspectives, A2B cooperation is conceptualized as a multidimensional construct covering types of collaboration, key actors and organizational drivers. Empirically, the study uses survey data from 298 firms operating in Albania, collected in 2025, and apply Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to examine the relationship between cooperation and sustainable innovation outcomes. The findings indicate that A2B cooperation remains limited and inconsistent, dominated by student internships and sporadic joint projects. However, companies are very interested in future partnerships on digital technologies, artificial intelligence, and green innovation. The analysis confirms that more intensive and better-structured cooperation is strongly linked with higher levels of sustainable innovation. The study is among the first quantitative assessment of A2B collaboration and sustainable innovation in Albania and provides policy and management implications for strengthening innovation-oriented partnerships, while emphasizing the need for comparative research across Western Balkan countries.

Keywords: Academia–business collaboration; sustainable innovation; Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), Innovation systems, Albania

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Received: 12 Dec 2025

E-mails: perseta.grabova@unitir.edu.al, arjan.tushaj@unitir.edu.al, ditjona.kule@unitir.edu.al, brikena.leka@untir.edu.al, sasa.petkovic@ef.unibl.org

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26. Elona Pojani, Perseta Grabova, Etleva Bajrami, Mirela Kamberi, Aligning Albania's Economic Policy with EU Climate and Energy Goals: Evidence from Multi-Stakeholder Roundtables and Documentary Analysis

Abstract

This paper assesses how far EU climate, energy, and sustainable-finance requirements are being embedded across Albania's energy policy subsystems and its fiscal and monetary frameworks, and how this affects economic development. It examines whether a coordinated, cross-sectoral approach is emerging in policy discourse, design, and implementation, and the degree of consensus among key actors. The study uses a mixed qualitative methodology: two stakeholder roundtables (government, civil society, academia, business) and a triangulated review of legislation, strategies, official reports, EU progress assessments, media, and expert-provided documents. By mapping the interplay between national priorities and EU directives, the paper gives actionable insights and targeted recommendations to align climate commitments with growth objectives. The goal is a coherent, resilient policy framework that both meets EU standards and advances Albania's long-term economic and environmental interests.

Keywords: EU climate and energy policy; economic policy alignment; sustainable finance; policy coordination; multi-stakeholder governance; policy coherence

RENGHINI MATTEO <m.renghini@pm.univpm.it>

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Special Issue - Second Edition

- *Pojani et al.*: [Aligning Albania's Economic Policy with EU Climate and Energy Goals: Evidence from Multi-Stakeholder Roundtables and Documentary Analysis](#)
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We sincerely thank you once again for your outstanding contribution to our [journal](#).

Kind regards,
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Economia Marche – Journal of Applied Economics

27. Gonçalves, A., Martins, A., Santos, D., & Serra, M., Economic Nutrition Label: Advancing Sustainable Tourism and Local Economies through Mediterranean Diet Products, Tourism & Management Studies

Abstract

The Economic Nutrition Label was created as part of the HoST Lab project, a creative culinary laboratory, that highlights the research activities and ingredients used to create gastronomic products associated with the Mediterranean Diet, promoting environmental sustainability and local economies. Similar to a nutrition label on food products, it provides information on the economic "ingredients", such as labour, raw materials or profit margin, and is a tool to promote sustainability, encourage companies to adopt more responsible production practices and drive tourism towards a more circular model. The HOST Lab successfully developed and tested an Economic Nutrition Label applied to innovative Mediterranean Diet products, such as carob semifreddo, olive oil spread, and carob gum cream cheese. The methodology provided a detailed breakdown of raw material costs, direct labor, and general overheads, offering clear insights into the economic distribution associated with each product.

Key words: Economic Nutrition Label; sustainable tourism; local economies; circular model.

TMS ALGARVE 2025:

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As Chair of the TMS Algarve 2025 conference, and in light of the approval of your paper titled “**Economic Nutrition Label: Advancing Sustainable Tourism and Local Economies through Mediterranean Diet Products,**” authored by **Alexandra Gonçalves, Manuel Serra, Ana Martins, and Dolores Santos**, I am pleased to propose its publication in the forthcoming volume of the **Springer Proceedings in Business and Economics, indexed in SCOPUS**. The provisional title of the book is Technology and Sustainability Challenges in Tourism, Hospitality and Management, although this may still be adjusted. Please note that the publication will involve inherent costs, which will be passed on to the authors.

José António C. Santos

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28. Imaginário, S., Santos, D., Barros, H., Vairinho, S., Rodrigues, J., & Martins, A.I. (Submitted). Dinâmicas de Inovação e Empreendedorismo no Algarve: O Papel da UAlg TEC START, Revista Portuguesa de Estudos Regionais

Abstract

This article analyses the impact of the university incubator UAlg TEC START (University of Algarve) within the innovation ecosystem in the Algarve region, framing its activities within the Quadruple Helix model and the role of universities as agents of technology transfer and regional development. The exploratory-descriptive research combines documentary analysis and descriptive statistics to assess indicators such as the evolution of the number of supported and incubated companies, survival rate, sectoral distribution, volume of investment mobilized and profile of the founders, as well as the physical characteristics of the incubator and the services provided. The results show a positive growth in the incubator's entrepreneurial activity, with a total of 241 companies created (since 2004) and a survival rate of 78% at three years, exceeding the national average. With regard to incubation, UAlg TEC START offers various incubation modalities, adopting a hybrid model that includes physical incubation, virtual incubation, and coworking. Among the incubated companies, there is a concentration in areas related to digitization and ICT (46%). The conclusions reached confirm the role of UAlg TEC START in promoting entrepreneurship in the region, fostering synergies between science, industry, government and civil society.

Keywords: UAlg TEC START; University of Algarve; university incubators; entrepreneurship;

innovation ecosystems.

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29. Imaginário, S., Santos, D., Vairinho, S., Barros, H., Rodrigues, J., & Martins, A.I., Innovation and Entrepreneurship Dynamics in the Algarve: The Role of UAlg TEC START, Tourism & Management Studies

Abstract

This paper analyses the impact of the university incubator UAlg TEC START (University of Algarve) within the innovation ecosystem in the Algarve region, framing its activities within the Quadruple Helix model and the role of universities as agents of technology transfer and regional development. The exploratory-descriptive research combines documentary analysis and descriptive statistics to assess indicators such as the number of supported and incubated companies, survival rate, sectoral distribution, volume of investment mobilized and profile of the founders, as well as the physical characteristics of the incubator and the services provided. The results show a positive growth in the incubator's entrepreneurial activity, with a total of 241 companies created since 2004 and a survival rate of 78% at three years, exceeding the national average. UAlg TEC START adopts a hybrid incubation model that includes physical incubation, virtual incubation, and coworking. Among the incubated companies, there is a concentration in areas related to digitization and ICT (46%). The conclusions confirm the role of UAlg TEC START in promoting entrepreneurship in the region, fostering synergies between science, industry, government, and civil society.

Keywords: UAlg TEC START; University of Algarve; University incubators; entrepreneurship; innovation ecosystems.

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29. Andjelković, A., Stošić Panić, D., Callejón Gil, A.M., Digital Transformation in the Retail Sector: Effects and Business Performance Analysis, Economic Themes

Abstract

Considering its impact on business performance, consumer behavior, and economic development, digitalization is a key driver in the retail sector. This study analyzes the level and effects of digital transformation in the retail sector of the Republic of Serbia. By examining data from the Statistical Yearbook of the Republic of Serbia and the financial and business reports of the seven largest retail chains (Delhaize Serbia, Lidl, Univerexport, AMAN, DIS, Gomex, and Metro Cash & Carry), the study investigates the correlations between the number of stores, employees, the presence of online sales, mobile applications, and loyalty programs, as well as financial indicators (ROS and ROE), and explores the potential impact of digitalization on financial performance. The results indicate that digital transformation in Serbia lags behind that of developed economies. While most chains offer mobile applications and loyalty programs, online sales remain limited. Moreover, despite the growing share of consumers shopping online, the impact of digital tools on financial performance is still low.

Keywords: digitalization, retail, online trade, performance

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31. Callejón Gil, A.M., Angel, M., Kocić, J., Radosavljević, M., Frugal Innovations as a Pathway to Inclusive and Resource-Efficient Entrepreneurship, *Facta Universitatis*

Abstract

In a global context shaped by resource constraints, unequal access to essential goods and services, and widening development gaps, frugal innovation has gained prominence as an approach to designing affordable, resource-efficient and context-appropriate solutions. Building on a structured review of recent literature, this paper first consolidates the conceptual foundations of frugal innovation and links them to debates on sustainability, inclusiveness and innovation ecosystems. It then advances an empirical analysis of how university ecosystems

support frugal innovation in a widening-economy context. Drawing on survey data from universities/technology transfer offices, the study operationalises key ecosystem dimensions—innovation infrastructure, educational and mentoring support, community engagement and metrics orientation—and examines their relationships with institutional support for frugal innovation and perceived innovation outcomes. Regression results show that stronger innovation infrastructure, frugality-oriented education and mentoring, and deeper engagement with local communities are all positively associated with institutional support for frugal innovation and with perceptions of affordable, locally relevant and market-viable solutions. By contrast, orientation toward frugal innovation metrics does not yet translate into significantly stronger perceived outcomes, suggesting that measurement frameworks remain largely conceptual and insufficiently embedded in practice. The paper offers policy and managerial implications for strengthening inclusive and resource-efficient entrepreneurship in widening economies.

Keywords: frugal innovation; inclusive innovation; resource efficiency; university ecosystems; technology transfer; community engagement; impact metrics; widening economies

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To whom it may concern

Confirmation of Manuscript Submission

I hereby confirm that the paper entitled:

"FRUGAL INNOVATIONS AS A PATHWAY TO INCLUSIVE AND RESOURCE-EFFICIENT ENTREPRENEURSHIP"

by **Angela Callejon Gil** (*University of Malaga, Spain*), **Manuel Angel** (*University of Malaga, Spain*), **Jelena Kocić** (*University of Niš, Faculty of Economics, Serbia*), **Marija Radosavljević** (*University of Niš, Faculty of Economics, Serbia*),

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32. Aleksandar Naumoski, Vesna Bucevska, Todor Tocev, Jasna Tonovska, Advancing Sustainability Concepts and Sustainability Reporting in the Western Balkans (WB-4): A Delphi Study on Corporate Practices, Journal of East European Management Studies

Abstract

The paper examines how corporate experts in four Western Balkan economies (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Serbia) understand, prioritize, and implement sustainability practices and sustainability reporting in SME-dominated, EU-accession contexts. A mixed Delphi-based design is used: two Delphi rounds with 20 experts and four national focus groups with 20 additional experts are employed to refine a survey, which is then administered to 100 enterprise-level experts across the WB-4, covering six thematic areas 1) environmental, 2) economic, 3) social aspects, 4) key challenges, 5) circular economy and 6) sustainability reporting.

There is strong consensus that environmental measures (especially energy management/efficiency and waste management) and economic aspects (employee training,

stakeholder cooperation, responsible business practices) are critical, while social aspects are endorsed but less consistently embedded in practice. Circular-economy actions and sustainability reporting are widely viewed as important, yet implementation remains uneven and often compliance-driven rather than strategic.

Experts highlight five main constraints: lack of skills and expertise, limited financial and technical resources, low transparency, unclear or weakly enforced legislation, and low public awareness, with some cross-country variation particularly around regulation and awareness levels. The study provides one of the first consensus-based, cross-country mappings of corporate sustainability concepts and reporting practices in the Western Balkans, offering concrete guidance for phased CSRD/ESRS alignment, capacity-building, and development of digital data systems, while also identifying avenues for future longitudinal and sector-specific research.

Keywords: ESG governance; Sustainability; Corporate social responsibility; Corporate strategic restructuring; Delphi study; Western Balkans.

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33. Vesna Bucevska, Todor Tocev, Milica Ristić Cakić, Macro drivers of national innovation in Southeast Europe: a cross-country panel analysis, Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship

Abstract

The paper investigates which macroeconomic, financial, structural, and institutional factors drive national innovation performance in eleven Southeast European (SEE) countries over 2014–2023.

Using an unbalanced panel (76 country-years), the authors model a composite Innovation Index (0–100) against 13 macro indicators (GDP per capita, capital investment, inflation, labor force, FDI, government spending, growth forecast, corruption, private credit, internet users, urbanization, industry value added, HDI). They apply fixed-effects panel regressions and an

EGLS specification with cross-section weights, after unit-root and full diagnostic testing for heteroskedasticity, serial correlation, and cross-sectional dependence.

Both models show high explanatory power (adjusted $R^2 > 0.90$). Inflation is a robust, negative and statistically significant determinant of innovation, while private-sector credit has a small but positive, borderline-significant effect. Internet penetration, unexpectedly, is negative and significant, revealing a “digital–innovation paradox” in SEE, where expanded access does not translate into higher innovative output. In the fixed-effects model, the Corruption Perceptions Index also loads negatively, suggesting complex and possibly paradoxical governance–innovation dynamics in the region, while most other variables are not statistically significant over this horizon.

The results highlight the need to safeguard macroeconomic stability (low inflation), steer finance toward productive, knowledge-intensive activity, and move from basic connectivity to higher-quality digital infrastructure and skills. Institutional reforms must go beyond improving perception-based governance scores and address enforcement gaps and informal practices that may blunt innovation incentives.

The study offers one of the first focused macro-panel analyses of innovation drivers in SEE, combining FE and EGLS with cross-section weights and revealing counterintuitive effects of internet use and perceived institutional quality that call for deeper, region-specific investigation.

Keywords: National innovation performance, Macroeconomic drivers, Southeast Europe (SEE), Panel data econometrics.

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34. Stojan Debarliev, Ljubomir Drakulevski, Vesna Bucevska, Bojan Kitanovikj, Which sustainability strategies pay? Unbundling the triple bottom line in companies, Cogent Business & Management

Abstract

The paper explores if the environmental, economic, and social aspects of the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) provide equal benefits to sustainable business practices. It also examines how

organizational drivers and institutional challenges affect these benefits in firms from the Western Balkans. By using a multi-phase research design, which includes a Delphi study with experts and a survey of 100 companies from Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, and Serbia, the study conducts multiple moderated regression analysis to test both direct and interaction effects.

The results indicate that economic and social sustainability have strong and significant direct effects on the perceived benefits of sustainability practices. In contrast, environmental sustainability does not provide significant benefits on its own. It requires strong organizational support, including formal strategies, partnerships, financial incentives, and employee engagement. Institutional and resource-related challenges greatly reduce the benefits of environmental initiatives. Economic and social outcomes remain mostly unchanged. By formally testing the equality of TBL effects, the study shows that sustainability benefits are not evenly spread across the pillars. This challenges the idea of balance in the TBL framework. The paper adds to the conversation by introducing a Strategy Activation Map. This map shows how environmental initiatives lead to real benefits only when supportive factors outweigh challenges in the context. The findings offer practical advice for managers and policymakers in developing economies. They suggest a careful order for sustainability actions: first, diagnose barriers; next, strengthen organizational drivers; and finally, activate environmental initiatives after establishing economic and social foundations.

Keywords: Triple Bottom Line (TBL); Environmental sustainability; Social sustainability; Economic sustainability; Sustainability benefits; Organizational drivers; Institutional and resource challenges.

[External] Cogent Business & Management - 250952505 - Your submission has proceeded to peer review

 Summarise

Cogent Business & Management <onbehalfof@manuscriptcentral.com>

To: Bojan Kitanovikj

Tue 21/10/2025 14:28

Cc: Bojan Kitanovikj

21-Oct-2025

QABM-2025-2969

Dear Dr Bojan Kitanovikj,

We have carefully checked over your above referenced manuscript, entitled "WHICH SUSTAINABILITY STRATEGIES PAY? UNBUNDLING THE TRIPLE BOTTOM LINE IN COMPANIES", and I am pleased to confirm that we will now send it for peer review in Cogent Business & Management.

Thank you for submitting to Cogent Business & Management. We will be back in touch in due course.

Best regards,

Jaydeep Vaghasiya, Shikha Sapkota, Praveen B
Cogent Business & Management Editorial Office

35. Stojan Debarliev, Aleksandra Janeska Iliev, Saša Petković, Marija Radosavljević, Ditjona Kule, From Symbiosis to Sustainability: University-Linked Centers as Catalysts in Academy to Business Ecosystems, Int. J. of Entrepreneurship and Small Business

Abstract

This study examines how collaborations between academia and business (A2B) contribute to addressing societal and environmental challenges in transitional and resource-constrained economies, with a particular focus on the role of university-linked centres such as incubators, accelerators, technology transfer offices, and research centres. While A2B collaboration is widely promoted as a driver of sustainable innovation, evidence from practice shows that its impact is often uneven, with many partnerships producing only limited or incremental results. Using a mixed-methods research design, the study combines a Delphi process with regional experts from Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, and Albania, and a survey of more than 100 managers and entrepreneurs active in regional entrepreneurial ecosystems. Mediation regression analysis is applied to examine how different dimensions of A2B collaboration—forms of collaboration, diversity of actors involved, and key collaboration elements—affect the ability of firms and ecosystems to address societal and environmental challenges, and whether these effects are mediated by the effectiveness of university-linked centres.

The results show that A2B collaboration has a strong and statistically significant direct impact on addressing societal and environmental challenges. Activities such as joint research projects, knowledge transfer, internships, and clearly structured collaboration mechanisms are consistently associated with positive sustainability-oriented outcomes. However, the mediating role of university-linked centres is asymmetric. These centres significantly mediate outcomes only when diverse actors are actively involved and ecosystem engagement is strong. In contrast, for collaboration forms and structural elements, the impact occurs mainly through direct interaction and hands-on cooperation, rather than through institutional intermediation. Overall, the findings indicate that university-linked centres become true catalysts only in actor-rich and well-connected ecosystems. Where networks are weak or collaboration is largely symbolic, direct engagement between academia and business is more effective than relying on formal structures alone. The study highlights that infrastructure and organisational arrangements, while important, are not sufficient by themselves; trust, active participation, and strategic alignment among actors are critical for achieving sustainable innovation outcomes.

From a practical perspective, the study provides clear guidance for policymakers, universities, and business leaders. To move from symbolic collaboration to real sustainability impact, priority should be given to strengthening stakeholder engagement, building trust-based networks, and supporting concrete collaboration activities. University-linked centres should be

empowered not only structurally, but also strategically, with a focus on facilitating actor interaction and managing innovation processes rather than serving as passive intermediaries. In conclusion, the research demonstrates that sustainable innovation in transitional economies is driven primarily by active, well-structured A2B collaboration, with university-linked centres playing a supportive but context-dependent role. Effective ecosystems are those where collaboration is lived in practice, not only designed on paper.

Keywords: entrepreneurial ecosystem, structured partnerships, developing countries, open innovation.

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Dear **Aleksandra Janeska Iliev**,

Thank you! You have successfully submitted your article "*From Symbiosis to Sustainability: University-Linked Centers as Catalysts in Academy to Business Ecosystems*" for the Int. J. of Entrepreneurship and Small Business.

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CONCLUSION

The analysis presented in this deliverable confirms that the USE IPM project has already generated a substantial and diverse body of scientific output, fully aligned with the objectives of WP1 and the overall Grant Agreement. A total of 34 papers have been submitted, some of them even accepted or published across reputable international journals, covering all four thematic areas of the project: soft skills and human capital development, sustainability and reporting, technology transfer and open innovation, and sustainable and responsible innovation through academia–business collaboration. These contributions draw directly on the empirical evidence collected through secondments, focus groups, Delphi studies and needs analyses, demonstrating both methodological rigor and strong internal coherence between research activities and dissemination results. The portfolio of papers spans different disciplines, methodological approaches and regional perspectives, thereby enhancing the project’s visibility and impact within academic, professional and policy-making communities.

The report also shows that partners consistently respect Horizon Europe Open Access requirements and acknowledge project funding, ensuring transparency, accessibility and long-term availability of knowledge produced within USE IPM. The breadth of co-authorship networks, involving researchers from all widening partners, indicates a growing integration of the Western Balkans and associated regions into European and international research ecosystems. Overall, this deliverable confirms that the project is on a very good trajectory regarding scientific dissemination: early results are already visible, the publication pipeline for the coming period is well established, and the generated evidence provides a solid foundation for subsequent work packages, further policy dialogue and future research on sustainable entrepreneurship, innovation process management and A2B collaboration in transitional economies.

ANNEX

Reviews of the D1.3 Report on submitted papers

Review 1	
Reviewer Name:	Dragana Radicic, SAB member
Date of review:	29/12/2025
Reviewer opinion: (150 words)	The deliverable “Report on submitted papers” is in the line with the Grant Agreement for the project No. 101120390. There is no need for further improvements of the deliverable by writer and other partners of the USE IPM consortium. General opinion: Accepted; Comments: No
Review 2	
Reviewer Name:	Sandra Milanovic Zbiljic, FEUN
Date of review:	29/12/2025
Reviewer opinion: (150 words)	The deliverable named “Report on submitted papers” is in the line with the Grant Agreement for the project No. 101120390. This document will serve as strong anchor for policy makers in Western Balkan countries. There is no need for further improvements of the deliverable by writer and other partners of the USE IPM consortium. General opinion: Accepted; Comments: No